

Title: Format specification for Near Real-Time format

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Near real-time file format version 2 (NRTv2 or just NRT) is used as an exchange and submission format for certain parts of the observation to archive and analyzes (O2A) dataflow framework developed at and hosted by Alfred-

Wegener-Institute (Koppe et al. 2015).

NRT files are supposed to contain time series data. Time series data necessarily is 1. in consecutive order, 2. ISO8601-compliant (International Organization for Standardization 2017), 3. free of duplicated rows, 4. free of duplicated timestamps, 5. free of trailing, leading, or in between blank/empty rows. Every column has a respective header, as well as every header (0th row) has as many columns in the first to nth row.

	O/M	Description
character encoding	M	UTF-8
field/column separator	M	tabulators [\t]
end of line marker	M	newline [\n]
column names	M	first column must be <code>datetime</code> followed by 1-n columns representing valid parameter URNs (uniform resource names following Masinter & Sollins (1994)) as used in registry.o2a-data.de to describe entities and relations
data values	M	decimal and integer values, character values only when unit is declared as [text]
no values	M	empty fields (null string or empty field respectively), see second to last row in table 2
decimal symbol	M	period [.]
datetime format	M	recommended: <code>yyyy-mm-dd HH:MM:SS.fff</code> , also supported: <code>yyyy-mm-dd HH:MM:SS</code> , <code>yyyy-mm-ddTHH:MM:SS.fff</code> , and <code>yyyy-mm-ddTHH:MM:SS</code> according to ISO8601, time must be submitted in UTC.
units	O	may be given in square brackets ([]), following each parameter URN, separated by a space
quality flags	O	quality flags can be added to each column of data by an identical parameter URN column followed by (quality flag). If submitted, conventions of Argo quality control flag scale for real-time and delayed-mode data (Argo Data Management Team 2025) must be applied.

Table 1: Technical and semantic conventions for NRTv2 files (O/M: optional/mandatory), figurative example can be found in table 2.

datetime	vessel:sonne:smb_sonne:smb_a_1702:salinity [PSU]	vessel:sonne:smb_sonne:smb_a_1702:salinity (quality flag)
2025-06-23 01:00:00.000	35.67900833333333	0
2025-06-23 01:01:00.000	35.67892033898305	0
2025-06-23 01:02:00.000	35.67851228070176	0
2025-06-23 01:03:00.000	35.67839259259258	0
2025-06-23 01:04:00.000	35.678136	0
2025-06-23 01:05:00.000	35.67816296296297	0
2025-06-23 01:06:00.000	35.67817627118642	0
2025-06-23 01:07:00.000	35.677966101694906	0
2025-06-23 01:08:00.000	35.67811333333334	0
2025-06-23 01:09:00.000		0
2025-06-23 01:10:00.000	35.678455	0

Table 2: Exemplary data of Self-cleaning Monitoring Box (SMB B) aboard RV Sonne (Schlundt 2025) following the NRTv2 file convention including quality flags (not applied in this case).

References

Argo Data Management Team (June 2025): Argo user's manual. Tech. rep. URL: <https://doi.org/10.13155/29825>.

International Organization for Standardization (Feb. 2017): ISO 8601 — Date and time format. URL: <https://www.iso.org/iso-8601-date-and-time-format.html> (visited on 06/25/2025).

Koppe, Roland; Gerchow, Peter; Macario, Ana; Haas, Antonie; Schäfer-Neth, Christian & Pfeiffenberger, Hans (June 2015): O2A: A Generic Framework

for Enabling the Flow of Sensor Observations to Archives and Publications. In: OCEANS 2015 Genova. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1109/OCEANS-Genova.2015.7271657>.

Masinter, Larry M. & Sollins, Karen R. (Dec. 1994): Functional Requirements for Uniform Resource Names. Request for Comments RFC 1737. Internet Engineering Task Force, 7. URL: <https://doi.org/10.17487/RFC1737> (visited on 06/26/2025).

Schlundt, Michael (June 2025): Self-cleaning Monitoring Box (SMB B) aboard RV Sonne. URL: <https://hdl.handle.net/10013/sensor.c70bda43-8608-4229-9bc2-b9ebb7ca5c97> (visited on 06/25/2025).